

Modeling Occurrences of Type 1a Supernovae and other End States of Common Envelope Evolution from a Third Star on a White Dwarf Inner Binary

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ABSTRACT

Hierarchical triple systems pose interesting questions in astrophysics, as the effect of the outer star could have a profound impact on the evolution of the inner binary and its potential to merge. A particularly intriguing case of triple systems are those with a double white dwarf inner binary system with a third outer companion. In this paper, we explore the effects of such a third star on the occurrences of double degenerate supernovae (WD-WD mergers) as compared to the standard WD-WD binary scenario. Specifically examining the cases where the third star is a giant overflowing its Roche lobe, causing its envelope to engulf the system of three stars, leading to an inward spiral of the orbits. Understanding the effects of the common envelope phase in triples is important, as it allows us to gain insight into how the consideration of a third star may affect our predictions for the occurrences of supernovae in WD-WD binaries. To compute the effect of the common envelope on orbital separations, we employ the SCATTER (Single Components' Angular momentum TransFER) formalism from [Di Stefano et al. \(2023\)](#), which uses angular momentum transfer to arrive at the final states of the system without needing to rely on complex hydrodynamical simulations or any of the underlying physics behind Common Envelopes. Instead by assuming circular orbits and using angular momentum conservation, whilst assuming angular momentum is transferred directly from stars to the envelope, SCATTER can solve for final orbital separations of Common Envelope evolution. For the purposes of our model, we consider our inner binary to be composed of 2 white dwarf stars with a red giant companion. We then run calculations to solve for the final orbital state of the system and determine whether it will merge within a Hubble time and what that merger will look like: a Type Ia supernova, an AIC (collapse into a neutron star), or a merger of low-mass white dwarfs. We find that for simulations of WD-WD binaries with an outer red giant star in the range of $0.8\text{--}6M_{\odot}$, common envelope evolution results in over twice the amount of supernova events, with roughly 2.5 times the overall frequency for mergers of the inner binary. Our results show that common envelope evolution could have a profound effect not only on the orbit of the inner binary but also on the outer binary, where, although all our systems are initially stable, we find roughly 4% will lose stability within a Hubble time after common envelope evolution, and another 0.5% will experience a second merger with the third star. With our results, we can then get an idea of how the consideration of a third star outside of a WD-WD binary could affect the occurrences of double-degenerate supernovae. Thus, our results help provide us with a better understanding of the evolution of triple systems and how such systems differ from the standard binary case. Such considerations are important as triple systems make up a substantial portion of known stellar systems (10% of F and G stars are home to triples ([Toonen, S. et al. 2020](#))). Our paper therefore helps establish the need for further investigation into triples as progenitors for type 1a supernovae.

1. INTRODUCTION

Common envelope evolution plays a highly influential role in the evolution of many multiple star systems as a result of an unstable form of mass transfer where a star overflows its Roche Lobe, leading to mass transfer on dynamical timescales as proposed in [Paczynski \(1976\)](#). The formation of a common envelope then leads to an in-

spiral phase where the angular momentum of the stars in the system is transferred to the envelope, eventually leading to either the ejection of the envelope or a merger of stars in the system ([Ivanova et al. 2020](#)). Common envelope evolution is broadly important for understanding the development of close binary systems. For the purposes of this paper, we focus on Triple Binary systems that could lead to potential Type Ia supernovae.

Type Ia supernovae primarily come in two forms; firstly, there is the single degenerate channel in which mass transfer from a hydrogen-rich companion onto a white dwarf pushes it over the Chandrasekhar limit, leading to a supernova. Secondly, there is the double degenerate channel which occurs primarily through the mergers of two carbon-oxygen white dwarfs. It is believed that double degenerate supernovae account for a significant fraction of Type Ia supernovae, but the specific portion of Type Ia Supernova that come from the double degenerate channel is not well agreed on. For a more complete overview of the different progenitor models one can refer to papers such as [Livio & Mazzali \(2018\)](#). One of the problems, however, with generating high amounts of double degenerate white dwarf mergers is that naturally occurring white dwarf binaries are often at too large of a separation to merge within a Hubble time simply due to the effects of gravitational radiation. Thus, in this paper, we focus on the double degenerate mechanism and try to investigate how the presence of a third companion might affect the allowed orbital separations which can form double degenerate Type Ia supernovae, and how there is further reason to investigate the effect of triples on Type Ia Supernova occurrences.

Much work has been done in order to understand the evolution of the common envelope phase, with hydrodynamical modeling having been done extensively to model the time evolution of common envelope systems as overviewed in [Ivanova et al. \(2020\)](#). However, for our work, we instead apply the SCATTER formalism as introduced in [Di Stefano et al. \(2023\)](#), as it is naturally well suited for calculating the final states of triple systems due to the model’s generalizability from the standard binary case. Thus this paper presents itself as the first in-depth numerical exploration of the SCATTER formalism.

In Section 2 we describe how we generate the triple stars in our model along with our application of the SCATTER formalism. Then in section 3, We provide an overview of our results, focus on the different outcomes arrived at by our model, and provide a comparison between the outcomes predicted by triple evolution as compared to standard binary evolution without common envelope evolution. In section 4 we discuss some additional considerations that are not included in our model such as the effects of three-body dynamics and the role of eccentricity. Section 5 concludes the paper by discussing further potential applications of the SCATTER formalism to look at the single degenerate channel of supernovae in triple-star systems.

2. MODEL

2.1. Setting Stellar Parameters

For the purposes of this paper, we considered a hierarchical triple system consisting of an inner WD-WD binary with an outer giant or subgiant star. We take the more massive star(M_1) in the inner binary to be either a CO(.5–1.1 M_\odot) or an O-Ne-Mg WD(.1.1–1.35 M_\odot), then we assume the companion WD(M_2) to have evolved second either as a HE(.2–.5 M_\odot) WD or a CO WD less massive than the first white dwarf. From there we generate the third star as an evolved star(red giant or subgiant star) within the mass range of $M_3 = .8\text{--}6M_\odot$. Additionally for red giant stars the Radius of the star is given by the core mass M_c ([Joss et al. 1987](#))

$$R \approx \frac{3.7 \times 10^3 M_c^4}{1 + M_c^3 + 1.75 M_c^4} R_\odot \quad (1)$$

However, this equation is only true in the range of $0.17M_\odot \lesssim M_c \lesssim 1.4M_\odot$ hence we want to constrain ourselves to core masses within this range. Such outer stars are those that will form White Dwarf remnants, so we can roughly construct an upper bound on the core mass of a given star through the mass of the WD stars they form. The mass of white dwarfs as a function of progenitor mass is given to us by the initial-final mass relationship established in [Cummings et al. \(2018\)](#)

$$M_f = (0.080 \pm 0.016) \times M_i + (0.489 \pm 0.030)M_\odot \quad (2)$$

$$(0.83M_\odot < M_i < 2.85M_\odot)$$

$$M_f = (0.187 \pm 0.061) \times M_i + (0.184 \pm 0.199)M_\odot \quad (3)$$

$$(2.85M_\odot < M_i < 3.60M_\odot)$$

$$M_f = (0.107 \pm 0.016) \times M_i + (0.471 \pm 0.077)M_\odot \quad (4)$$

$$(3.60M_\odot < M_i < 7.20M_\odot).$$

Thus we can use M_f as an upper bound on M_c for a given star, as M_f represents the core mass of the giant at the end of the AGB, thus providing us with a somewhat reasonable upper bound on the core mass. From there we then set our lower bound to be $0.17M_\odot$ and sample evenly between those two bounds to calculate for M_c . Additionally, we set our envelope mass as $M_e = M_3 - M_c$ thus providing us with all our relevant stellar parameters¹. From here we apply the the constraint of the critical mass ratio q_{crit} for whether a common envelope will form. There exist many formalisms for q_{crit} as given in ([Hurley et al. 2002](#)), and more recently ([Ge et al. 2020](#)), however for our system it is

¹ In practice for equation (3) we reduced the error substantially when generating our model to get a more realistic set of parameters the high error originated from a set of outliers in the original paper

reasonable to simply use $q_{\text{crit}} = 1$ where we only select systems that have values of $q > q_{\text{crit}}$ where $q = \frac{M_3}{M_1 + M_2}$. From here we can now generate all our stellar parameters by sampling randomly between the bounds set for M_1 , M_2 , M_3 , and M_c in order to get a relatively even distribution across our parameter space. To better visualize this the parameters for the third star are shown in the figure below.

Figure 1. Plot of Envelope, Core mass, and Radius for the third star in the binary.

2.2. Triple Orbital Parameters

To generate our triple we can first start from generating our inner binary. For this, we will simply sample from a set of reasonable merge times that will allow us to best view the effects of the common envelope, setting an upper bound at which even with Common Envelope evolution the system results in near-zero interesting end states. To do this we take the merge time equation given as:

$$T_{\text{merge}} = \left(\frac{1.5 \times 10^8 \text{yr}}{M_1 M_2 (M_1 + M_2)} \right) [(a_{\text{in}}^4 - a_{\text{min}}^4)] \quad (5)$$

Where a_{min} represents the separation of the two bodies at the time of merging which we treat as zero as $a_{\text{min}} \ll a_{\text{in}}$. Sampling from merger times of 1.5×10^5 and 1.5×10^{25} we get the following bounds for our inner binaries orbit:

$$a_{\text{in}}^{\text{min}} = \frac{1.5 \times 10^5}{1.5 \times 10^8} * ((M_1 + M_2) M_1 M_2)^{.25} \quad (6)$$

$$a_{\text{in}}^{\text{max}} = \frac{1.5 \times 10^{25}}{1.5 \times 10^8} * ((M_1 + M_2) M_1 M_2)^{.25} \quad (7)$$

From here we can now generate the orbital parameters of the third star through logarithmic sampling between these two bounds. Since we want to look at potential

common envelope-forming stars we only select stars that fill their Roche lobe(or are near the point of expected Roche lobe filling) thus using the following definition of the Roche lobe from (Eggleton 1983) we have:

$$r_L(q) = \frac{0.49q^{2/3}}{0.6q^{2/3} + \ln(1 + q^{1/3})} \quad (8)$$

Where our effective Roche lobe radius is given by:

$$\frac{R_L}{a_{\text{out}}} = r_L(q) \quad (9)$$

Thus providing us with a simple way of calculating for a_{out} by setting $R = R_L$ to set the star at the point of Roche lobe filling(stellar radius equal to Roche lobe radius) and thus find the orbital separation of our outer binary.

2.3. The common envelope:

From our generated system parameters we then applied the common envelope formalism to find our end-states. The final equation for orbital separation as determined by the SCATTER formalism is given as:

$$\frac{a(f)}{a(0)} = \left[\frac{(1+q)(1+q_{\text{ec}})^2}{1+q(1+q_{\text{ec}})} \right] e^{[-2\mathcal{F}(q,\delta)(10^{B+\Delta} \times (\frac{q_{\text{ec}}q}{1+q})^{1-A})]} \quad (10)$$

With the function $\mathcal{F}(q, \delta)$ given by:

$$\mathcal{F}(q, \delta) = \mathcal{Q}(q, \delta) \frac{1}{q} + \mathcal{Q}\left(\frac{1}{q}, \delta\right) q \quad (11)$$

Where the function \mathcal{Q} defines a fraction of CE mass affecting the angular momentum of an individual star. Thus the fraction of relevant common envelope mass for angular momentum transfer with the envelope for each star is given by $\mathcal{Q} * m_e$, and our equation for \mathcal{Q} is provided by:

$$\mathcal{Q}(q, \delta) \equiv \frac{[r_L(q)]^\delta}{[r_L(q)]^\delta + [r_L(q^{-1})]^\delta} \quad (12)$$

Where q is given as the mass ratio between the donor and the companion while q_{ec} is a mass ratio of the core mass over the envelope mass. δ meanwhile is simply a dimensionality parameter corresponding to 3. The values of A, B, Δ are empirically determined from post-CE systems as given in Table 2 of Di Stefano et al. (2023).

For the case of the outer binary this calculation is relatively straightforward as we know the donor is of mass M_c (remaining mass of the third star after loss of envelope) and has an effective companion of mass $M_1 + M_2$ corresponding to the inner binary, so we can simply plug in for our value of a_{out} with $q = \frac{M_c}{M_1 + M_2}$ and $q_{\text{ec}} = \frac{M_c}{M_c}$

However for the case of the inner binary, we need to be a bit more careful as in a sense there is no true donor star to the system as we are only considering M_1 and M_2 thus we want to consider an effective inner envelope bounded by the two stars so we can declare our effective envelope mass to be $M_{e\text{in}}$ given by $M_{e\text{in}} = m_e \cdot \mathcal{Q}(\frac{M_1+M_2}{M_3}, \delta)$. Thus we are using our \mathcal{Q} function to find the fraction of CE mass that causes drag on the inner binary, and then from there, we can divide that envelope mass up into how it affects the two stars in our inner binary individually. We then can roughly equate the more massive star in the inner binary M_1 to be our donor for this new effective common envelope and then take the less massive star M_2 to be our companion such that we have $q = \frac{M_1}{M_2}$ while $q_{ec} = \frac{M_{e\text{in}}}{M_1}$ and from there we are now able to run our calculations to determine the final states of the system.

3. RESULTS

Once we computed the final inner and outer orbital separations we then used our equation for merge time as given in equation 5 to find the merge time for the inner(T_{in}) binary and the third star with respect to the inner binary (T_{out}). From there we divided our results into their potential outcomes: No Merger of inner binary($T_{\text{in}} > T_{\text{hubble}}$), a merger that fails to produce a supernova instead forming a more massive white dwarf($M_1 + M_2 < M_{\text{chandrasekhar}} \approx 1.4M_{\odot}$), a merger that produced a Type 1 a Supernova, and mergers that produce an Accretion Induced Collapse(AIC). Note that for AICs we only consider those that form through the merger of an Oxygen-Neon white dwarf($M_1 \vee M_2 > 1.1M_{\odot}$) and another white dwarf. However, under certain conditions, AIC's can form from a merger of two CO WDs, but that is outside the scope of our work, for a more comprehensive overview of AIC progenitors one can refer to Wang & Liu (2020). Additionally, it is also important to consider the effects of the common envelope on the outer binary. For this, there are two main cases to consider. The first of which occurs when $T_{\text{out}} < T_{\text{in}} < T_{\text{hubble}}$, in this case, our system will have a complete loss of stability and will end in chaos thus making it impossible to know whether a merger will happen. Secondly, we have the case where our inner binary manages to merge, and rather than having a Type Ia supernovae either ends in accretion-induced collapse or a merger into a sub $1.4M_{\odot}$ mass white dwarf. In this case if $T_{\text{out}} < T_{\text{hubble}}$ the system will have a second merger take place between the remnant core of our third star with the compact object produced by the merger of the inner binary. There are 5 sets of possible outcomes that can result from this second merger.

If the first merger produced a more massive WD and we have $M_C + M_2 + M_1 < 1.4M_{\odot}$ then we have the merger produce an even more massive WD, while if the sum of masses is over the Chandrasekhar limit we have a type 1a supernova, or if one of the white dwarfs was an O-Ne-Mg White Dwarf we have an Accretion Induced collapse. On the other hand, if the first merger ended in an AIC we can either have a merger into a more massive neutron star or if we exceed the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff(TOV) limit(which we set as $2.3M_{\odot}$) then we say we our second merger forms a Black Hole.

We then display the set of all such results for the triple along with a set of results for the end states of a set of identical binary systems where we simply removed the presence of the third star, as shown in Table 1. From this table, we can see a large increase in mergers as a result of common envelope evolution, and a small portion of systems that end with a second merger. However, it is important to consider the fact that our results do overestimate the rates of all our outcomes(AICs, Type Ia supernovae, and BH formation) as they assume no mass loss occurs during each merger event. As such it is especially important to note that predictions for second mergers such as BH forming systems are most likely overestimating such numbers and our results for BH formation are an extreme statistical improbability, and further work must be done to see if such outcomes are indeed possible.

To get a better idea of when merger and supernova events should happen refer to the histogram in Figure 2 to see when our model predicts a merger of the inner binary after CE evolution(Divided into the cases of Type 1a, AIC, and mergers into more massive white dwarfs). We can see the clear impact common envelope evolution has on the change in merge time of our triple compared to the standard binary. We note that for inner binaries of similar orbital separations, those that are subject to common envelope evolution from an outside star have a large decrease in merge times from that point, with roughly 3-4 times as many systems merging within a Hubble time as opposed to the standard binary. While further work needs to be done to additionally benchmark how long it would take these systems to form and reach a point at which CE filling would begin, our results still show that Triple Evolution could constitute a large part of type 1a supernovae especially early on in the universe. Thus this result shows the importance of triples when considering the effects of type 1a supernova may have had on the early universe and the importance of creating a more realistic population synthesis that better considers system formation time to more effectively ascertain the true effects of triples and CE evolution.

To better visualize our results we can plot the set of all outcomes for the WD-WD binary along with our triple system to see the what effects adding a third star that forms a common envelope can have on the set of possible outcomes. As we can see in Figure 3 our results are mostly as expected with the triple system showing a set of outcomes for a far wider set of initial orbital separations, as seen in the difference in the bounds of both graphs. As we can see in our plot for the triple system our drop off in outcomes occurs at around $10^{2.5}$ – 10^3 as opposed to $10^{0.5}$ – 10^7 for the case of the binary, thus we can see that the consideration of a third star being added to a WD-WD system could allow for the mergers of inner binaries with upwards 100 times the orbital separation of a similar system without a third star. On top of this common envelope evolution allows for a large number of systems to end in chaos at the higher orbital separations as well, showing that even at the highest generated orbital separations at our model the common envelope allows for events to occur. Albeit it is hard to understand the effect chaotic systems can have as outcomes as while the system could be brought apart it is also possible for such systems to end in mergers as well. Furthermore, Common Envelope evolution has the effect of stabilizing orbits during formation which has the potential to further impact what makes a system chaotic. Thus while our results provide a decent estimate of chaotic systems further work would need to be done to better understand such systems. Additionally, in the triple case, we continue to see sparse amounts of events occur even beyond $10^{2.5}$ as opposed to the hard cutoff in the standard binary case, with systems ending in AICs and Type 1a Supernovae up to separations of $10^4 R_{\odot}$.

Looking at the mass distribution of results in the plot we can first note the hard cutoff at the Chandrasekhar mass as we would expect between our AIC/Type Ia systems and our white dwarf forming systems. Within the low mass range, we also find the highest number of chaotic systems and second merger forming systems. We can best understand this by noting that the more massive component of the system will proportionally lose a greater amount of angular momentum as a result of the SCATTER formalism so these systems have proportionally greater angular momentum losses by the third star which we can see visualized in the left side of figure 4 where systems with higher values of q (which generally correlates with lower inner binary masses) have the greatest change in orbital separation of the outer binary. This thus leads to the third star being able to fall into the inner binary within a Hubble time, and in cases where the initial orbital separation of the inner binary is

large enough (beyond our rough merger bound of around $10^{2.5} R_{\odot}$) we see most of such systems end up in chaos, while below this bound we see a higher number of second mergers.

In addition to this, we also looked at how different parameters would affect the change in orbital separation. For our equation for merge time we can note that our two relevant variables were q and q_{ec} we can see this relationship visualized in Figure 4. It is somewhat interesting to note that the greatest change in separation came at lower q values in the inner binary, to better understand these relationships we can refer to Figure 5 where we plotted the changes in orbital separation we found by plugging in various values for q and q_{ec} that are relevant for both inner and outer binaries into equation 11 to see how our two input variables modify our outcomes. Such plots mirror those done in Figure 8 of Di Stefano et al. (2023), but over a range of parameters more applicable to our generated system. As we can see for the set of q values for the inner binary we can note that we see a minimum right past $q = 1$ which is confirmed in our orbital evolution relationship as one would expect. Furthermore, we can see that increasing envelope mass does indeed have the expected effect of lowering our orbital separation for the inner binary.

Table 1. Comparison of outcomes within a hubble time for standard white dwarf binary and triple system with common envelope phase.

	WD-WD Binary	Triple With CE
No inner merger	863661	433651
Merger(No SN)	76834	277975
Type Ia	26608	113655
AIC	32897	135689
Chaos	-	39030
Second Merger	-	4896
Second Merge into WD	-	2388
Second Merge Ia	-	2408
Second Merge AIC	-	12
Second Merge With NS	-	35
Second Merge into BH	-	53
Avg log merge time inner	16.34 ± 4.92	9.61 ± 5.1
Avg log merge time outer	-	13.27 ± 2.03

NOTE—For the Average Log merge time values in addition to providing averages the \pm values indicate the standard deviation of merge times. Additionally the Second Merge with NS category only describes cases where the NS and the remnant core merge into another neutron star.

Figure 2. Histogram showing set of log merge times for the inner binary as measured from the point of common envelope evolution in the case of triple evolution (Blue) and log merge time starting from an identical initial inner orbital separation for a standard WD-WD binary. The corresponding Cumulative Probability plot is also shown (black for triple, red for binary case). The top plot represents the time taken for Type Ia supernovae to occur in all possible progenitor systems, while the middle and bottom plots represent the same thing but for AIC progenitor systems and systems that simply merge into a more massive white dwarf respectively. Additionally, there is a dotted blue line in all of the figures that represents 1 Hubble Time.

Figure 3. Plot of inner binary mass vs log initial orbital separation (R_{\odot}) for both our modeled triple (top) and the inner binary with the third star removed (bottom) with the color of each point representing the outcome for the system (within a hubble time) as given by 1. Blue dots indicate systems with mergers that do not result in supernovae. Green dots represent type 1 a forming systems, red dots are systems that end in an AIC, black dots represent triple systems that ended in chaos, and the large purple dots are systems which experiences a secondary merger.

Figure 4. Plot of q and q_{ec} for both inner and outer binaries note that for the inner binary the mass of the envelope for the inner binary is the mass the computed value of M_e in While the color indicates the log change in merge time with darker values representing a greater change in the merge time of the system.

Figure 5. The left two plots represent the effect of different values of q_{ec} for a continuous spread of q values has on the change in orbital separation of the binary by plugging into equation 11. The right set of plots meanwhile have continuous q_{ec} values and sets of lines for various values of q . The top two plots in the graph refer to the Inner Binary and thus have $q = \frac{M_1}{M-2}$, and $q_{ec} = \frac{M_{ein}}{M_1}$ while the bottom two represent the outer binary with $q = \frac{M_c}{M_1+M_2}$, and $q_{ec} = \frac{M_e}{M_c}$ thus corresponding to the left and right plots of 4 respectively

On the other hand for the case of the outer binary the relationship is more complex as while generally we see that higher q values lead to greater decreases in orbital separations we can also note that for low q values (just below 0.4) we find the common envelope leads to larger merge times and a higher value of q_{ec} leads to an even higher increase in orbital separation. We see some of this on the left side of figure 4 as with increasing q_{ec} at low values of q we do see higher and higher increases in orbital separation as predicted in figure 5. In addition to this, we see that for higher q values our relationship becomes more similar to what we would expect as we see that an increase in q_{ec} leads to smaller and smaller final orbital separations.

While such results may seem strange at first they are in fact expected outcomes within the SCATTER formalism and such increases in orbital separation at low q values for WD-MS systems have a similar increase in orbital separations at low q values as we found for our outer binary. This is expected as low q values mean the inner binary is relatively more massive and thus the inner binary has a much greater contribution to angular momentum exchange. Meanwhile, the third star's loss of envelope mass means that depending on how much angular momentum is lost by the core during the common envelope phase, it is entirely possible for the outer star to in fact be sent further from the inner binary. One can understand this by noting that low core mass values will correspond to higher values of $M_{e\,in}$ thus these are systems that have much higher shrinkages of the inner binary as a far greater portion of the Common Envelope affects the Inner Binary as opposed to the third star. Generally however greater envelope mass should lead to greater shrinkages in merge time which is rather unsurprising as a relatively more massive envelope means a larger amount of angular momentum that will be extracted from both orbits thus leading to smaller final orbital separations after the common envelope.

4. DISCUSSION

As we have found in our results the common envelope evolutionary phase in triples does as expected lead to more mergers and supernovae over a wider set of orbital separations compared to the WD-WD binary. However, there are numerous considerations that remain within our results. Firstly we choose to ignore the effects of the more complex three-body dynamics within the system, and we assume circular orbits which may not necessarily be the case given the potential effects of the Lidov Kozai mechanism. Especially within the context of the fall in of the outer third star in the system, the effect of chaos is not necessarily negligible. Nevertheless, the

large shrinkages in our outer binaries orbit do create some cause for consideration on the effects the common envelope phase may have on the system's stability, as while we provided an estimate of chaotic systems we did this largely ignoring the effects of more complex three-body dynamics. Thus it is likely that our model underestimates the number of triple systems that truly end with chaos.

Additionally, it is also worth considering that our model predicts a much-heightened count of accretion-induced collapse events as compared to the isolated binary. Thus common envelopes from a third star could allow WD-WD binaries with a wider set of initial orbital separations to collapse into neutron stars. However, it is worth considering that accretion-induced collapse events have yet to be observed despite them having long been theoretically predicted, thus raising questions about any AIC predictions. In addition to this our model also could have some considerations towards the portion of Type Ia supernovae that originate through the double degenerate channel as standard population synthesis approaches such as [Toonen, S. et al. \(2012\)](#) generally neglect to include the influence of triple systems on the frequency of double degenerate supernovae. However, to be able to make any concrete claims about how triples would affect double degenerate rates a more realistic population synthesis would be required. All we can claim from the results of our paper is it is clear that triples do have a non-negligible impact on occurrences of double-degenerate supernovae.

5. CONCLUSION

In our paper, we have demonstrated how the common envelope phase of triple evolution can lead to far heightened rates of type 1 supernovae through the double degenerate channel as opposed to the standard compact WD-WD binary system. While the work done in this paper has allowed us to gain deeper insight into some aspects of triple common envelope evolution much work remains to be done, especially in investigating systems that are capable of initiating mass transfer. Firstly one of the main goals following up on the paper will be to perform a more realistic population synthesis process to create a more representative sample of binaries and triples to properly assess the real effects triples would have on the observed rates of type Ia supernovae among other events. This would also allow us to determine roughly when in the universe we would expect these systems to form, and thus get ideas as to when triple evolution could allow for the first Type Ia supernovae to occur. Additionally, within the context of Type Ia

supernovae, it is important to consider the single degenerate channel as well. Examples of such possibilities could be to instead consider a set of systems with a single compact object in the inner binary and look at how common envelope evolution from a third star could lead to mass transfer and eventually a Type Ia supernovae within the system. Furthermore, while we considered cases where the tertiary star in the triple is the one to form the common envelope there are also often cases where one of the inner stars instead is the one to overflow its Roche lobe and form a common envelope, which also leads to considerations of the third star falling in and initiating mass transfer. Thus while we have es-

tablished the importance the SCATTER formalism has in application towards triples within the case of double-degenerate Type Ia Supernovae, there remains much left to be investigated within the context of the SCATTER formalism for common envelope.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank Dr. Rosanne Di Stefano (Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics) for working as my advisor for this paper, and additionally, I would like to credit Professor Chiaki Kobayashi (University of Hertfordshire) for her feedback.

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